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THE INFLUENCE OF MUSIC ON THE FORMATION OF MUSICAL CULTURE OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

Karimova Dildora Anvarovna

Associate Professor of Tashkent State Pedagogical

University named after Nizami

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Abstract: This article discusses the influence of music on the formation of musical culture in preschool children. Also, information about the psychological conditions of preschool children will be covered.

Key words: Musical education, culture, education, individual approach.

Introduction.

Preschool age is the most important stage of personality development and upbringing, the period when children's cognitive interest and curiosity develop. Therefore, in pre-school educational institutions, it is necessary to organize activities to cultivate artistic taste in preschool children, to form creative skills in them, and to educate musical culture.

The musical culture of D. B. Kabalevsky's child personality was connected with the spiritual understanding of musical art. He believed that musical literacy is a musical culture that is manifested in the qualities of music perception:

- the ability to perceive music as a living figurative art born from life and inextricably linked with life;
- a special "*musical sense*" that allows to perceive it emotionally, to distinguish the good from the bad in it;
- the ability to determine the nature of music by ear and to feel the internal connection between the nature of music and the nature of its performance.

Y. B. Aliyev defines the musical culture of a child as an individual socio-artistic experience that determines the emergence of higher musical needs. At the same time, musical culture is understood as an integral characteristic of a person, its main indicators are:

- musical development (*love for musical art, emotional attitude towards it, need for various examples of artistic music, musical observation*);

- musical education (*arming with the methods of musical activity, knowledge of art studies, emotional and value attitude to art and life, new knowledge about art, development of musical and aesthetic ideals, artistic taste, critically selected attitude to various musical phenomena*).

O. P. Radynov considers the musical culture of a preschool child as an integral personal quality formed in this process:

- systematic, targeted education and training based on emotional sensitivity to high artistic works of musical art;
- musical-figurative thinking and imagination;
- accumulation of intonation cognitive and value experience in creative musical activity;
- the development of all components of musical and aesthetic consciousness, i.e. aesthetic feelings, emotions, interests, needs, taste, ideal ideas (*there are age limits*), which affects the emotional and evaluative attitude of the child to music causes, actualizes in the manifestation of aesthetic and creative activity.

In the works of these authors, an active search for new forms and methods of teaching children in music lessons was conducted. Therefore, it is impossible not to agree that musical development has a profound effect on the overall development of a young child. Thanks to this, an emotional atmosphere is formed, thinking improves, the child becomes sensitive to the beauty and life in art.

The volume of musical culture suitable for preschool age is received by the child in the family, in kindergarten, through mass media, music and cultural institutions. The influence of the family on the formation of a child's musical culture is determined by its traditions, the attitude of family members to the art of music.

The role of the kindergarten is manifested through the personal and professional qualities of the teacher-musician, his talent and skills, the general cultural level of the teachers and the entire team of teachers, the conditions they create.

Thus, the basis of a child's musical culture can be considered to be his musical and aesthetic consciousness, which is formed in the process of musical activity. The components of the structure of a child's musical culture include: musical experience, musical literacy, and musical and creative development. Musical experience, according to L. V. Schoolboy, allows to assess the musical interests of the child, his inclinations, the breadth of musical and life characteristics. The perception of music and the experience of playing it show the orientation (*or lack thereof*) in the values of the musical heritage of the past (*classical, musical folklore*) and in the musical life of the modern environment.

The criteria of experience can be: the level of general awareness of music, the presence of interest, certain preferences and benefits, the child's motives for

turning to a certain music, that is, what the child looks for in it and what he expects from it.

Musical literacy is a person's ability to perceive music as a living, figurative art born from life and inextricably linked with life; a special "*sense of music*", which allows you to perceive it emotionally, distinguish the good from the bad in it; the ability to determine the nature of music by ear and feel the internal connection between the content of the music and the nature of its performance, as well as the ability to identify the ear of an unknown author of music, if it is specific to this author.

The musical and creative development of the child is considered as the ability of creativity and self-development in the integrated system of musical culture. Creativity is an indicator of human development, and in music it is the highest indicator of a person's mastery of the art of music. Musical creativity is manifested as self-knowledge, self-expression and self-affirmation in their unity. The need for self-expression is manifested when the child expresses his attitude to the moral and aesthetic ideals present in art, self-knowledge, the child expresses his spiritual world through music, self-affirmation it is revealed when he learns through music - when he declares himself, the richness of his sexuality, his creative energy.

Music can influence the development of a child's creative personality, stimulate moral and aesthetic experiences, lead to active perception and change of the environment, and active thinking. Like fiction, theater, and visual arts, the art of music performs the most important social function. For example, influencing music is sometimes more powerful than persuasion or demonstration. Children should be encouraged to empathize when introducing them to works with different emotional educational content. Thus, the song about the motherland evokes a feeling of love for the Motherland. Round dances, songs, and dances of different peoples arouse interest in the traditions of the peoples of the world and cultivate international feelings. Genre wealth of music helps to perceive heroic images and lyrical mood, cheerful humor and lively dances. Different emotions that arise when perceiving music enrich children's experiences, enrich their spiritual world.

Educational tasks are mainly solved in collective singing, dancing, games, when children are covered by common experiences, as a single action is required from the participants. They create a useful ground for individual development. The example of friends, general inspiration, the joy of performance activates timid, indecisive children. For children with attention disorders, a change in

confidence in the successful behavior of other children serves as a brake on negative manifestations.

Music lessons affect the general behavioral culture of a preschool child. Changing the types of activities: singing, listening to music, playing children's musical instruments, requires children to show attention, ingenuity, reaction speed, organization, voluntary actions. For example, when playing a song, you need to start and end it on time. Being able to move to the rhythm of music in dances and games. All this improves the child's willpower.

At an early age, the baby distinguishes music from the surrounding sounds and noises. He focuses on the heard tone, concentrates for a while, listens, smiles, walks, responds with individual movements. Older children understand some connections between events, are able to make the simplest generalizations - for example, to determine the nature of music, name, game is happy, cheerful, calm or sad. They also understand the requirements: how to sing different songs in nature, how to move in a quiet round dance or a moving dance. Musical interests are also formed: preference is given to a certain type of activity, music genre. The first manifestations of artistic taste are observed in children between the ages of six and seven: the ability to evaluate works and their performance. Singing voices at this age have melodiousness, melodiousness, and mobility. The range is evened out, vocal intonation is more stable, most six-year-old children sing without instruments.

The famous psychologist and pedagogue Lev Semyonovich Vygotsky called the unity of formation of the emotional and intellectual spheres of the child's psyche, the unity of influence and mind as the most important condition for the harmonious development of the personality. Musical education is a unique tool for the formation of this unity, because it has a great impact not only on the emotional, but also on the cognitive development of the child, because music not only conveys feelings, but also a huge world of ideas, thoughts, images.

Music is one of the bright means of aesthetic education of children, aimed at developing preschool children's ability to perceive, feel and understand beauty, good and bad. Acquaintance with real beauty forms aesthetic feelings, which become the basis of aesthetic taste, aesthetic feelings, feelings and judgments. It opens the world of creative development for the child, contributes to his socialization and prepares him for the life of a full-fledged adult.

Music, as a means of forming the child's moral image, directly affects the child's feelings, forms his moral image. According to L. S. Vygotsky, genetic forms of behavior regulation in childhood remain emotions for a long time, and

perhaps they play a role in regulating the formation of personality as a holistic education in the process of development.

Research into the phenomenon of music has shown that the human brain uses many areas to listen to music. The left side of the brain usually controls rhythm and pitch, while the right side controls timbre and melody. Perception of music by listening is one of the most abstract ways of thinking that requires special mental attention, the ability to maintain attention and emotional stress. Children listen to sound, compare similar and different sounds, get acquainted with their expressive meaning, note the characteristic semantic features of artistic images, learn to understand the structure of the work.

Answering the teacher's questions, after listening to the piece, the child makes the first generalization and comparison: determines the general feature of the performance, emphasizes that the literary text of the song is clearly expressed by musical means.

Cognitive abilities are developed thanks to various topics of familiarization with musical games, round dances, artistic movements. When listening to a piece of music, children are interested in its content. They have questions about wanting to know what the music is talking about. Individual displays of musical memory appear. Listening to music develops the child's ability to clearly distinguish the surrounding world, makes the child more observant and sensitive.

Creative musical tasks help the emergence of a child's search activity, which requires mental activity. For example, when singing, the child improvises, creates his own version of the melody, tries to find the correspondence of the literary text with expressive intonations. In musical and rhythmic activities, children with great pleasure invent dance moves, combine them, sing songs and move to music. Dance, folk dance, pantomime, and especially musical and game dramatization encourage children to describe a picture of life, describe any character using expressive movements, facial expressions, and words. In this case, a certain sequence is observed: children listen to music, discuss the topic, assign roles, then act. At each stage, new tasks will appear that will force you to think, imagine, create.

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